

Use of ZnO as a photocatalyst in photocatalytic bleaching of Rhodamine-B

Riyaj A. Mansoori, Sharad Kothari and Rameshwar Ameta*

P. G. Department of Chemistry, Government College, Banswara-327 001, India

E-mail : jayfine123@rediffmail.com

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The photocatalytic bleaching of Rhodamine-B (Rh-B) over zinc oxide powder was carried out in presence of light. The photocatalytic bleaching of dye was observed spectrophotometrically. The effects of various parameters like concentration of Rh-B, pH, amount of semiconductor, surfactant, light intensity on the rate of the photocatalytic bleaching were observed. A tentative mechanism for the photocatalytic bleaching of Rh-B is proposed.

Sharma *et al.*¹ investigated the photocatalytic bleaching of orange-G in aqueous ZnO solutions. Artem *et al.*² reported the effect of amount of TiO₂ on the rate of photobleaching of methylene blue whereas Chen and Chau³ reported the photobleaching of methyl orange in aqueous solution with suspended TiO₂. The photobleaching of methylene blue sensitized by TiO₂ was studied by Andrew Mills and Jashum Wang⁴ in the presence and absence of oxygen. Xie *et al.*⁵ reported photoassisted degradation of dyes in the presence of Fe³⁺ and H₂O₂ under visible light. Kim and Yoon⁶ used TiO₂/Y-zeolite as a photocatalyst for photoreduction of methyl orange in aqueous solution. Richard *et al.*⁷ reported that oxidizing species involved in photocatalytic transformation on ZnO is either hydroxy radicals or holes. Ying Ma and Jian Nian Yao⁸ prepared a thin film of TiO₂ and used it to study photodegradation of Rh-B. Devi and Krishnaiah⁹ used various heat-treated TiO₂ as the photocatalyst for photocatalytic degradation of *p*-aminoazobenzene and *p*-hydroxyazobenzene. Dagan and Tomkiewicz¹⁰ used TiO₂ aerogels for photocatalytic decomposition of aquatic environment. Vamathevan *et al.*¹¹ used silver-modified TiO₂ particles for photocatalytic oxidation of organics in water. A literature survey revealed that no work has been reported on the photocatalytic bleaching of Rh-B over ZnO. This was the motivation behind the present work.

Results and discussion

The photocatalytic bleaching of Rh-B was observed at $\lambda_{\max} = 526$ nm. The optimum condition was obtained at [Rh-B] = 0.70×10^{-5} M, light intensity = 26.80 mW cm⁻², pH = 9.50, ZnO = 0.50 g and temperature = 308 K.

$$\text{Rate} = k [\text{Rh-B}]$$

$$k = 2.303 \times \text{slope}$$

The plot of $2 + \log$ O.D. vs exposure time is a straight line which indicates that the photocatalytic bleaching of Rh-B follows pseudo first order kinetics.

Effect of pH variation : The effect of variation of pH on the rate of photocatalytic bleaching of Rh-B was investigated and reported in Table 1. ZnO dissolves in the presence of highly acidic media and therefore photocatalytic bleaching could not be investigated in lower pH range.

The rate of photocatalytic bleaching of Rh-B increases with increase in pH up to 9.5 and then decreases with increase in pH value above 9.5. This behaviour may be explained on the basis that the increase in the rate of photocatalytic bleaching may be due to the increased availability of OH⁻ at higher pH values. By combining with holes, OH⁻ ions will generate more hydroxyl radicals (OH[•]) which are considered responsible for the photocatalytic bleaching.

Above a pH value of 9.5, the more OH⁻ ions will compete with the electron rich dye. The OH⁻ ions will make the surface of the semiconductor negatively charged and as a consequence of repulsive force between two negatively charged species (OH⁻ ions and the electron rich dye) the approach of Rh-B molecules to the semiconductor surface will be retarded. This will result in a decrease in the rate of photocatalytic bleaching of Rh-B dye.

Effect of variation of dye concentration : The effect of variation of dye concentration on the rate of the reaction was also studied by using different concentration of the Rh-B solution. The results are given in Table 1.

It was observed that as the concentration of Rh-B is increased, the rate of photocatalytic bleaching also found

Table 1. The dependence of the pseudo first order rate constant (k) for the photocatalytic bleaching of Rh-B on various parameters at 308 K

pH ^a	$k \times 10^5$ s ⁻¹	[Dye] ^b $\times 10^5$	$k \times 10^5$ s ⁻¹	ZnO ^c /g	$k \times 10^5$ s ⁻¹	[NaLs] ^d $\times 10^5$ m	$k \times 10^5$ s ⁻¹	I^e mW cm ⁻²	$k \times 10^5$ s ⁻¹
6.00	6.48	0.20	5.01	0.10	3.00	0.00	0.73	10.20	5.25
6.50	6.67	0.30	5.60	0.20	4.25	1.96	1.96	14.60	6.00
7.00	6.75	0.40	6.15	0.30	5.40	3.84	2.23	22.50	6.85
7.50	6.89	0.50	6.40	0.40	6.85	5.66	2.90	26.80	7.36
8.00	7.03	0.60	6.96	0.50	7.36	7.40	3.40	32.40	8.50
8.50	7.17	0.70	7.36	0.60	7.36	9.09	3.65	37.50	8.81
9.00	7.26	0.80	7.25	0.70	7.37	10.71	3.85	40.80	9.26
9.50	7.36	0.90	7.00	0.80	7.36	12.28	4.00	50.00	10.40
10.00	7.31	1.00	6.65	0.90	7.35	13.79	4.16		
10.50	7.22	1.10	6.00						
11.00	7.12								
11.50	6.94								
12.00	6.85								

^a[Rh-B] = 0.70×10^{-5} M, ZnO = 0.50 g, light intensity = 26.80 mW cm⁻².

^bZnO = 0.50 g, pH = 9.5, light intensity = 26.80 mW cm⁻².

^c[Rh-B] = 0.70×10^{-5} M, pH = 9.50, light intensity = 26.80 mW cm⁻².

^d[Rh-B] = 0.70×10^{-5} M, pH = 9.50, ZnO = 0.50 g, light intensity = 26.80 mW cm⁻².

^e[Rh-B] = 0.70×10^{-5} M, pH = 9.50, ZnO = 0.50 g.

to increase, reaching a maximum at 0.70×10^{-5} M. Further increase in concentration resulted into a decrease in the rate of photocatalytic bleaching. It may be due to the fact that as the concentration of the dye was increased, more dye molecules were available for excitation and for energy transfer. But if the concentration of Rh-B was increased above 0.70×10^{-5} , the dye will start acting as a filter for the incident light. It will prohibit the desired light intensity to reach the dye molecules near the semiconductor particles and thus a decrease in the rate of photocatalytic bleaching.

Effect of amount of ZnO : The effect of variation of amount of ZnO on the rate of the photocatalytic bleaching of the Rh-B was also observed. The results are reported in Table 1. It was observed that the rate of reaction increases with increase in the amount of ZnO (0.50 g). Beyond 0.50 g, the rate of reaction becomes constant. This may be due to the fact that in the initial stage as the amount of semiconductor increased, the exposed surface area of the semiconductor also increases, but after this limiting value (0.50 g), any further increases in the amount of semiconductor will not increase the exposed surface area but increases the thickness of the semiconductor layer.

Effect of surfactant : The photocatalytic bleaching of Rh-B was also studied in the presence of surfactant (so-

dium lauryl sulphate/NaLs). The rate of photocatalytic bleaching increases with the increase in concentration of sodium lauryl sulfate. The results are reported in Table 1.

It may be due to the fact that the anionic surfactant will be adsorbed on the surface of semiconductor, therefore, a unimolecular anionic layer of the surfactant will be formed on the surface of the semiconductor. This anionic layer attracts the cationic dye molecules towards itself. This will facilitate the approach of the dye molecules to the surface of the semiconductor.

Effect of variation of light intensity : The effect of variation of light intensity on the rate of photocatalytic bleaching of Rh-B was observed. The results are reported in Table 1. It may be due the fact that increase in light intensity increases the rate of photocatalytic bleaching. As the intensity of light increases, the number of photons striking per unit area of the semiconductor (ZnO) also increases. A linear behaviour between light intensity and the rate of reaction was observed. Since an increase in the light intensity increases the temperature of dye solution and a thermal reaction may occur, therefore, higher intensities were avoided.

Mechanism :

On the basis of the observed data, the following tentative mechanism may be proposed for photocatalytic

bleaching of Rh-B.

When the solution of the dye was exposed to light, in presence of zinc oxide, initially the ${}^1\text{Rh-B}_0$ molecules are excited to first excited singlet state (${}^1\text{Rh-B}_1$). Then the excited molecules are transferred to the triplet state through inter system crossing (ISC). The triplet dye (${}^3\text{Rh-B}_1$) may donate its electron to the semiconductor and the dye becomes positively charged. The dissolved oxygen of the solution will pull an electron from the conduction band of the semiconductor, thus, regenerating the semiconductor.

The positively charged molecules of the dye (Rh-B^+) will immediately react with OH^- ions to form OH^\bullet radicals will convert the dye molecules into products, which are colourless. The participation of OH^\bullet as an active oxidizing species has been confirmed by carrying out same reaction in presence of some hydroxyl radical scavengers like 2-propanol, where the rate of bleaching was drastically reduced.

Experimental

Rh-B and zinc oxide were respectively obtained from Reidel and Merck. The stock solution of Rh-B was prepared in doubly distilled water. Some controlled experiments were carried out to confirm that reaction follows photocatalytic pathway. 0.50 g of zinc oxide was added to 50.0 ml [$0.70 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$] Rh-B solution. The desired

pH of the solution was adjusted by addition of previously standardized $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{NaOH}$ solutions. The pH of the solution was measured by a Systronics digital 335 pH meter.

A Mysore 200W tungsten lamp was used. The intensity of light was measured by a Surya Mapi (CEL-SM-201) solarimeter. A water filter was used to cut-off thermal radiations. The progress of the reaction was measured using a Systronics 166 spectrophotometer. For absorbance measurements the solution was made free from ZnO particles and other impurities by centrifuging.

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